

10C3 Understanding Coupling Processes and Dynamics between Cities and Climate: the urbisphere project

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Cities are among the key drivers of climate change due to energy and resource consumption, a large number of vehicles and building construction. Cities have also been affected by the climate change threats such as heatwaves, drought, sea-level rise, and flooding. Responding to such socio-natural phenomena demands interdisciplinary approaches. Inclusive and effective mitigation and adaptation strategies to enhance urban climate resilience need to be based on a sound understanding and quantification of the drivers of climate change as well as changes in socio-economic and urban features. Such an integrated approach however requires novel observational, modelling and assessment frameworks. Recognising this challenge, urbisphere project aims to forecast and project urban future and climate in a dynamic framework considering the weather, air quality, and differential exposure and vulnerability of people at the neighbourhood to city scale. This will be done through developing and optimizing a unified modelling system to represent physical-human dynamics. Such a coupled modelling approach will incorporate both urban form (e.g. settlement types and physical structure of cities) and urban function (e.g. human behaviour and mobility). This paper is going to particularly focus on the vulnerability assessment framework in the project. It examines the question that how physical form and socio-demographic characteristics influence susceptibility, adaptation options and overall the adaptive capacity of people e.g. to heat stress. It

further explores how heat stress affects human behaviour and mobility pattern. To investigate the above questions, an integrated conceptual framework is developed to incorporate multiple concepts such as the link between (climate) exposure and (human) vulnerability, climate change parameters, socio-demographic indicators, and urban development. Local scenarios will be built to capture socio-demographic changes and dynamics of human vulnerability. Remote sensing and observation data will support the scenarios of exposure and vulnerability assessment e.g. in terms of land use patterns and urban change. The methodology will be applied to the cities of Stuttgart and Berlin, where a household survey will be conducted. The questionnaire explores multiple parameters such as risk perception of residents, building profile and open spaces information, mobility of households and its dynamics, climate profile of the neighbourhood (e.g. experience with heat stress), and measures to enhance coping and adaptive capacity. Information from the household survey and statistical data will be coupled with remote sensing data to identify and cluster differential socio-economic and demographic profiles linked to different settlement types. The results from this assessment will be used to capture the vulnerability and capacities of residents living in different settlement types to deal with heat stress. This will further inform both mitigation and adaptation policies e.g. in terms of modifying urban form and function and land-use planning.